

ANCIENT SCULPTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article aims to develop aesthetic education in students by teaching them the past heritage of sculptural art. As a basis for this, the artifacts found in the Surkhodarya region as a result of archaeological excavations from the II-IV centuries BC were used as a basis. We hope that these resources will help students to enrich their understanding of the way of life and culture of our ancestors who lived in the 30s, and to expand their imagination of our historical culture.

Keywords: *sculpture, archeological, empire, Kushons, data*

Sculpture is one of the oldest forms of art, and it has had its own direction and meaning in each period. Looking into the past, we see that the art of sculpture has been developing since ancient times. "Nefertiti" created by the Egyptian sculptor Thutmes, or "Disc Thrower" by the Greek sculptor Meron, "Dancer" by Skopas

"Moneda" sculptures are a good example of this. Including the samples dating back to the 2nd - 5th centuries that were found as a result of excavations in Dalvarzintepa, Khalchayon, Kampirtepa, Bolaliktepa, Afrosiyob, the ancient Khorezm Tuprok fortress, Jonbos fortress, and a number of regions of our country. It shows that the art of sculpture has a long history in Uzbekistan. In particular, the "Mother and Child" image of the gods, found in the Tuprok fortress, is especially valuable because of its perfection. The original carpet has not reached us because it was buried under the soil.

In Central Asia, including in the territory of Uzbekistan, the ancient monuments of BC have been thoroughly studied. But according to the information found and verified so far, it shows that in the previous centuries, art and culture were at a high level in Central Asia. This is a great opportunity to learn about the future of our people. For example: L. I. Rempel's "Architectural ornament to Uzbekistan", G. A. Pugachenkova's "Architekturnye pamyatniki Nis", M. T. Aminjonov's "Kissa of Ancient Monuments" contains a lot of information about the influence of the Greeks and local peoples on the monuments found in the lands of Central Asia before the Arab conquest.

In October 1932, soldiers of the border guards 13 km from Termez. above, a statue of three musicians (playing a harp, lute and drum), lying in the water near Ayritom, carved on a stone slab between the leaves of an akanfa tree in relief method, is found in Amudarya After a certain period of time, this statue will be brought to Tashkent to the Committee "Preservation of Historical Monuments and Cultural Assets". This discovery was the main impetus for the beginning of large-scale excavations to find and study historical monuments throughout our country in the future.

After antiquarian scientists became convinced that this statue is very ancient, M. E. Under the leadership of Masson, a working group was formed and sent to Surkhandarya region, and as a result of the excavations conducted by them in Ayritom, many unique objects were found: pottery, jewelry, coins, and examples of sculpture. The most exemplary types of visual and practical art objects found in the territory of our country belong to the period of the Kushan dynasty.

The culture of the Kushon era, which left an indelible mark not only on the history of the peoples of Afghanistan, Pakistan, and India in Central Asia, but also on the history of the peoples of the whole world, is the progress of human development.

the 1st - 2nd centuries BC. Every person will be amazed by the samples of art and cocktails found. Because most of the Buddhist sculptures are anatomically perfect.

In order to create works of art at a high level, human consciousness and thinking must be at a high level. These sculptural examples show that the people's lifestyle, art, science and culture were at a high level during the reign of the Kushan Empire. The period in which this country lived is called "Kushon period" in history. The Kushan period covers the period from the end of the 1st century BC to the middle of the 4th century AD. The center of this great empire, which occupied the lands from the Indus Valley to Parthia, was the northern and eastern lands of India, that is, present-day Afghanistan.

According to written sources, the mighty "Big Yuechki" tribe, after conquering the Greco-Bactrian branch, settled on the south bank of Amudarya and divided into five principalities: Khumi, Shuami, Khisa, Dumi and Guyshuang. Kuchmanchi tribes are the branch of Bactria's rich traditions, developed state system and highly developed culture. The Bactrians were much higher than the Kuchmanchis with their socio-economic system. Therefore, they began to exploit the achievements of the Bactrians. This was not only the wish of the powerful clans, but also the necessity of the development of the society. First of all, the tribal governors began to solve the trade and money exchange, which had developed rapidly in Bactria. Due to their lack of experience in producing new coins, they began minting coins in the simplest way, imitating the coins of Eucratides and Heliocles circulating in these regions. Coins imitating the coins of Heliocles in Karaganda were widely circulated during this period. On the obverse side of the coins is the head of an unknown horn, and on the obverse side is a relief of a horse on an urn with the statue of the Greek god Zeus. It is known that the peoples of Central Asia, especially the Kuchmanchi tribes, glorified and worshiped horses. The reason is that most of these coins were found in Surkhandarya region.

It is assumed that these coins were minted by governors of the Kushan-Guishuan region. Placing the image of a horse on coins indicates that a new state is emerging here. Coins with the image of a horse are found mainly in the vicinity of Dalvarzintepa and Kholchayan. Based on this, G. A. Pugachenkova calculates that "Dalvarzintepa, the capital of the Kushon-Guishuan region, was in urn." In the second stage of the development of the new state, the image on the front of the coins changed. It depicts a statue of a horn.

His face is similar to the statues found in Kholkhayon. On the reverse side of the coins there is a figure of a horseman and four words written in Greek letters. The first word is hukumron, the second word is Geray, the third word is not yet pronounced, and the fourth word is kushon Thus, it was determined that the name of the first ruler from the Kushon-Guishuan clan was Geray. But there is a lot of information about when Gerai came to power. Many researchers consider him to have ruled in the second half of the first century BC. According to some sources in the Chinese annals, about a hundred years after the "Yuechi" tribe conquered Bactria, the governor of Guyshuan, Kadphiz, defeated the Yuechki tribes and declared himself the "Kushon ruler".

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